

$p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ for Identical Photons the Basic Idea Behind the Bose-Einstein Distribution? Part 2

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In Part I, we noted that a classical minimal informational distribution of total energy E among N particles, treating the particles as identical and following: $E = \sum_{i=1}^N e_i$ (where $b \leq N$) leads to $p(e_i)$ unnormalized = $\exp(-e_i/T)$ ((1)). In other words, this is a minimal information approach applied to identical particles. In quantum mechanics, given that particles have wavelengths and frequencies, they are not physically identical particles receiving some energy. The kinetic energy they receive actually seems to transform their identity. Thus, as argued in Part I, only photons with the same frequency ν are considered to be identical and the minimal informational idea of ((1)) only applies to E_ν , the energy associated with photons with frequency ν . The problem is that one does not know what E_ν , only E_{total} , and one does not know how many photons with ν are present. Nevertheless, ((1)) holds and so the notion of entropy is linked with groupings of ν photons in a fixed number of N_ν cells (obtained from a phase space shell with $4\pi^3 \cdot 14 \text{ pp dp Volume} / (h \text{ power } 3)$ representing the number of shells and $E=pc$ for a photon.

In other words, what seemed like a classical idea, namely minimal information for an E distribution over N particles, seems to also hold in quantum statistical mechanics. As a result, it seems to be a universal idea.

It seems that Planck, by suggesting that electromagnetic energy of frequency ν is linked with specific photons (particles) of energy ν introduced a way for one to distinguish ν photons from ν_1 ones. Thus, the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach of distributing energy over N identical particles now only holds for the identical ν . An energy of ν is a distinguishing feature that does not allow one to distribute energy according to the minimal information approach ((1)) over different ν , ν_1 , ν_2 photons, only among photons with the same ν .

At first this property may seem to only apply to photons, but $E=pc$ follows from $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) which holds for both photons and particles with rest mass. In the photon case, it is known that they have a physical frequency (wavelength) from prism and 2-slit experiments and so ν as photon energy is linked to this frequency. There is a physical distinguishing feature linked to momentum and energy and one may apply this idea to particles with rest mass as well, namely ones called bosons. Thus, the ideas used for the photon should also apply to bosons with the same e_i .

The question we then ask here is why if one writes a reaction balance equation for two body collisions of bosons, do there exist enhancement factors so that $p(e_1)$ which would normally be the probability for $p(e_1)$ to interact becomes $p(e_1)(1+p(e_3))$ if e_1 scatters into e_3 ?

The Importance of Identical Particles in the Maxwell-Boltzmann Scheme

It is known from the Gibbs-paradox that Maxwell-Boltzmann particles should be considered as identical. If one has N particles with total energy E , this energy is distributed among the particles. If one thinks then only of energy distribution, one has:

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^b e_i \quad \text{where } b \leq N \quad ((2))$$

If one wishes to have minimal informational probability $p(e_i)$, then such a probability cannot contain any more information than ((2)). Here we use unnormalized probabilities and the notion of an AND rule for $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. If $e_i=0$, then $p(e_i)=1$ so that it contributes nothing to the product. Then one finds that:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad \text{i.e. represents single particle energy } ((3))$$

In other words, probabilities multiply and energies add, but otherwise the two schemes are completely compatible for a minimal informational scheme which we argue applies to a Maxwell-Boltzmann -Shannon picture.

What if Particles are Not Identical?

This leads to the following problem. Light was originally thought of as a particle by Newton, but then the view changed and it was considered a wave when interference experiments were performed in the early 1800s. These waves are not identical because they are linked with a colour (visible range) which is associated with a frequency and wavelength (whether there is a visible colour or not). Light, however, can strike a target and for a transition of an electron in an atom there is a certain single energy (delta energy level) electromagnetic object which is produced, which also has a frequency and wavelength. Thus, there is a notion of a particle, but it is one that is physically identified with a wavelength and frequency. In other words, photons with different frequencies (or energy= h frequency) are physically different, not identical. Thus, the Maxwell-Boltzmann notion that one may distribute total energy E over N fixed particles does not seem to hold if there are photons of different frequencies vs. This Maxwell-Boltzmann notion, however, is equivalent to a minimal informational picture, we argued, and so is a general argument. It should apply to all photons with the same vs as we argued in Part I. From this idea, one may obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution as explicitly shown in Part I.

Here we ask: What does one do with particles with rest mass?

Particles with Rest Mass

The photon relation $E=pc$ (associated with the wave equation $c = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$) follows from the special relativistic expression:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((4))$$

As a result, if a photon is distinguished by having a wavelength and frequency for a given E, p , one might expect the same for a particle with rest mass. Two-slit experiments show that this is the case. Just as photons with different vs are distinguishable, but ones with the same vs are not, the same idea should apply to particles with rest mass, at least for the subset called bosons. (Fermions are a different matter and are not considered here.)

The minimal informational picture should apply to bosons of the same energy e_i . If one has a boson gas with total energy E and an average number of particles N (grand canonical picture), one may have any number of particles with e_i , i.e.

$$p(e_i) = \exp(- (e_i - u) * n / T) \text{ unnormalized } ((5))$$

((5)) is the minimal informational principle applied to a fixed e_i . One must then sum over n to obtain the partition function Z

$$Z = \text{Product over } i \text{ Sum } n=0, \text{ infinite } z \text{ power } n \exp(-n e_i / T) \text{ where } z = \exp(-u / T) ((6))$$

$$= \text{Product over } i \text{ } 1 / (1 - \exp(- (e_i - u) / T)) ((7))$$

from which one may find:

$$\langle n(e_i) \rangle / N = d/dz \ln(Z) \text{ taking the } e_i \text{ piece } ((7))$$

This leads to the Bose-Einstein result if one uses the sum of a geometric series to solve ((6)).

$$\langle n(e_i) \rangle / N = p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized} = 1 / \{ \exp((e_i - u) / T) - 1 \} ((8)) \text{ (see (1) for more details)}$$

$$\text{One may then find that: } e_i / T = \ln\{ (1 + p(e_i)) / (p(e_i) z) \} ((9))$$

The question then becomes: How does one describe a reaction balance?
In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, two body elastic scattering is given by:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \text{ if } e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l ((10))$$

This is the minimal information result because the two particles are considered identical. In the boson case, this minimal information result only applies to particles with the same energy. Thus, $p(e_1)$ is the probability to have an e_1 which may react, but if it becomes an e_3 , then there is an increase in the entropy of e_3 particles which is different than if it becomes e_3' . The effect of this e_3 entropy is linked with ((7)). In other words, one does not consider isolated interactions, but must worry about the entropy of identical particles, i.e. the identical e_1 s, the identical e_2 s, e_3 s and e_4 s because the system is supposed to be in equilibrium, i.e. in a maximum entropy state.

If one wishes to use elastic scattering, then ((9)) shows that there is an entropy enhancement factor of $(1 + p(e_i))$ which differs with $p(e_i)$ (unnormalized), i.e.

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \rightarrow p(e_1)[1 + p(e_3)] p(e_2)[1 + p(e_4)] = p(e_3)[1 + p(e_1)] p(e_4)[1 + p(e_2)] ((11))$$

This enhancement factor is due to the increase in entropy if an e_1 becomes an e_3 , hence increasing the entropy among the identical e_3 particles. This idea has to be applied for all four cases, e_1, e_2, e_3 and e_4 as shown in ((11)).

Entropy considerations apply to boson elastic two-body scattering because of the increases in entropy of e_3 identical particles when a particle e_1 becomes an e_3 etc. It is not enough to write $p(e_1)$ for an e_1 particle entering a reaction. One needs to consider the effects its conversion into an e_3 have on entropy of e_3 particles. There is no such consideration in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann-Shannon minimal informational unnormalized probability $\exp(-e_i/T)$ applies to the distribution of an energy E over identical particles. In the case of photons, different e_i photons represent different frequencies ν_i and so are not identical. We argued in Part I that one may not use the MB minimal informational $p(e) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ across different ν_i 's, but can use it among identical ν_i 's. We saw in Part I that there were N_i cells of ν_i photons, but that one does not know the number of i photons, nor their total energy E_i . One only knows E total. Nevertheless, the amount of energy of ν_i photons in a cell with i photons is $i * \nu_i$ and so $\exp(-C i \nu_i)$ is the probability. From this, we calculated the Bose-Einstein distribution for photons.

Here we argue that since $E=pc$ for a photon follows from $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m^2c^4$ ($c=1$) which holds for particles with rest mass, there should be the possibility for these massive particles to also have a frequency and wavelength which makes particles with different e_i values distinguishable. (This holds for bosons.) In such a case, one has entropy linked with each e_i value, not across the board as in the MB case. One may find that the Bose-Einstein distribution again exists if one assumes any number of particles with energy e_i and writes a sum of unnormalized probabilities, i.e. the partition function $Z = \text{Product over } i \text{ Sum over } n \exp(-n e_i/T)$ and uses the sum of a geometric series. Using $p(e_i) = d/dz \ln(Z)$ where $z = \exp(-u/T)$ one may obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution and then solve for e_i/T . This yields $e_i/T = \ln((1+p(e_i))/ (p(e_i)z))$. ((B))

If one considers an elastic collision of bosons, then an e_1 may become an e_3 . There is a probability $p(e_1)$ to have an e_1 , but if it becomes an e_3 , one must worry about the increase in entropy of identical e_3 particles, something that one does not have to consider in the MB case. Using the result ((B)) one may see that the increase in entropy is proportional to $(1+p(e_3))$ so $p(e_1)$ is now $p(e_1)(1+p(e_3))$ and the same idea applies to e_2, e_3 and e_4 in a reaction balance. Thus, reaction balance with increases in entropy of product states is equivalent to ((B)).

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bose%E2%80%93Einstein_statistics